

Massive Open Online Course
A PRACTICAL GUIDE FOR SARS-COV-2 WHOLE-GENOME SEQUENCING

About the course

SARS-CoV-2 genomics surveillance has been proven pivotal for the management and control of the COVID-19 pandemic. However, genomics capacity is still limited, particularly in low-and-middle-income countries (LMICs). This course will provide tools and resources for capacity building aiming to strengthen the genomics surveillance approaches

Learning outcomes

- Compare sequencing methodologies
- Critically evaluate different approaches to determine SARS-CoV-2 genomes and variants
- Identify ways in which to scale up SARS-CoV-2 sequencing
- Describe SARS-CoV-2 analysis pipelines

Target audience

This course is designed for diagnostic and healthcare professionals, researchers, and anyone involved in the testing and analysis of COVID-19 samples.

Material repository website

https://wcscourses.github.io/COG-Train_Resources/practical_guide_home.html

Content

Week 1 Fundamentals of viral sequencing

Glossary

Introduction to viral genomes

Learning more about SARS-CoV-2 genome

Why viral genome sequencing is important

How to sequence using Illumina technology

Why was Nanopore sequencing used in the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic?]

Using metagenomics to investigate infections

What is viral whole-genome sequencing

Using sequencing to investigate SARS-CoV-2

SARS-CoV-2 sequencing workflow

Why you should collect metadata

How to handle primary samples

Storing high-quality samples

What happens to samples after sequencing

Assessing the quality of nucleic acid

Week 2 Library preparation and sequencing

How to isolate good quality nucleic acids

What a targeted sequencing protocol

How SARS-CoV-2 primer sets were designed

Producing SARS-CoV-2 amplicons

Checking the quality of amplicons

What is a sequencing library and how is it prepared?

Comparing library preparation methods

Illumina: pooling samples and loading cartridges

Nanopore: pooling samples and loading flow cells

How SARS-CoV-2 has been sequenced around the world

Comparing manual and automated methodologies

How to avoid contamination

Coordinating human resources in a pandemic

How to plan ordering and tracking of reagents

Legacies of the COVID-19 pandemic

Week 3 Sequencing analysis and interpretation

What are sequencing metrics

Accessing and using sequencing data

How to generate a consensus sequence

User-friendly tools for quality control

Why high-quality data is important

What are clades, lineages and variants?

SARS-CoV-2 Variants

Interpreting Nextclade quality metrics
Lineages classification using Pangolin
Introduction to phylogenetics: tools and models
How to detect an outbreak
Generating public health reports
How to prevent sequencing and sampling bias
Using sequencing data to identify outbreaks in a hospital
The importance of sample and data consent
Establishing collaborations in a pandemic
Challenges and how to overcome them
Resources

Collaborators

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Original version

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<https://www.futurelearn.com/courses/a-practical-guide-for-sars-cov-2-whole-genome-sequencing/1>

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